

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume I, Issue I | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

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“UNRAVELING TRUTH”

The four walls of the classroom maybe wide
Where stories were shared and dreams collide
These young learners are dreaming bright
Inspired by their teacher’s values and insights

Bounteous books and lessons are found
With tapestry of wisdom earned by young minds
The teacher thrives with doubts and fears
But seen only are the best as she delivers

The teacher watches and understands
The fragile strengths in trembling hands
She wears her mask to cover hitches
For she needs to look great always

Each learner has story to tell
To a fine teacher with an open ear
A journey shared a dream to take
Guided by the teacher to reach that peak

And in the unraveling, she finds
A deeper heart and inmost mind
The teacher’s truth, a devoted soul
To guide and nurture a learner as a whole